

Misc. Notes
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GS/ST. /R16 /①-⑤

PL.

7/1/80 Finished cleaning of area. Excavation of 1st section of trench (Locus 2~~9~~). (See general plan) 25 cm. Bank left at 3 margins of square to allow for collapse and later cleaning of profile. AREA of MUD with stone chips similar to that visible on surface in locus EXPOSED AND ISOLATED (SECTIONED in LCU.2) charcoal removed from NE. section of square in level 2.

Little to no ANCIENT cultural material in 1st 2 levels. CONTAMINATION EVIDENT - Rubbish (SURF + lev 1)

PITS + ~~THE~~ camel thorn Roots.